

MSc GEM Course 2009/2010

Lund University

Advanced GIS Course

GIS PROJECT: INVESTIGATION OF THE LAKE VICTORIA REGION

Module 1 and Module 2

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Model 1. Description of Brief Conceptual Model of the Database Preparation

1) Description of the Source Data used

For the Victoria Lake region GIS Project we have the following thematic data available:

- Shape files of **administrative boundaries** (ArcGIS compatible format .shp), separately for Uganda, Tanzania and Kenya. Each .shp file has also additional supporting files like as .shx and .prj, which show additional information about projection, metadata etc. Also available UNEP grids for the same territories
- **Precipitation climatic** data in .txt format, containing meteorological data in digital format: precipitation values in different months and years.
- **Digital Elevation Models (DEMs)** showing relief characteristics and elevation of the research area. Data are taken from USGS website. There are two available data of GTopo30 - E020N40.DEM covering territory of Kenya and Uganda, and E020S10.DEM showing south-eastern part of Tanzania. DEM files contain horizontal grid spacing of 30 arc seconds (approximately 1 kilometre).
- **Land Cover data** in raster format which is stored in .bsq format: IGBP.bsq. This file is a part of the global land cover characteristics database. The pixel values correspond to class numbers defined in the appropriate land cover classification scheme legend. The data projected in the Lambert Azimuthal Equal Area projection for the Africa land cover characteristics.
- **Population data** were downloaded from the UNEP website. They contain raster data for the whole Africa continent. We have chosen two years for our research – data for 1990 and 2000 years. Each dataset had two different files – population density (popd00 and popd90 respectively) and population total.
- As an additional data set we need miscellaneous data containing **Landsat ETM+** images in MrSid format - S-36-00_2000.sid.

2) Files formats and Operations needed to import the data to GIS programme

The administrative boundaries data are initially in **.shp** file format, so that we only need to re-project them to necessary projection (Africa Albers Equal Area Conic). The DEM data were initially zipped in tar.gz so that we extracted them via WinZip Manager in order to add them into the GIS project. Both DEM files contain part-files in specific format - **.DEM, .DMW, .gif** file and **.HDR** extension. DEM files are necessary for reading information about elevation heights and relief. The Africa land cover characteristics in Land Cover data **IGBP.bsq** is a flat, raster format. Population data are stored in world file **.twf** format which we opened in ArcGIS as **.tiff** raster files and re-projected to the Africa Albers Equal Area Conic projection.

To import both raster and vector data we used “**Add Data**” function.

3) Initial Spatial extent and how relevant data should be extracted

Initial spatial extent of the population data was for the whole Africa, and we needed to clip the necessary raster area from the whole territory. To do this we used ArcToolbox instruments: Data Management Tools / Raster / Raster Processing / Clip.

To clip necessary area we used raster file covering the whole area of interest (three countries and Victoria lake), which in turn was received by using Spatial Analyst function "Import vector to raster" of vector file afadm_lvr.shp.

Administrative boundaries data were correct and contained only the required extent.

4) Initial geographic reference / transformation procedures needed

Files were initially in different projections and we need to transform each vector file to the Africa Albers Equal Area Conic projection. For that purpose we used ArcCatalog, where we changed spatial information directly in file by right-clicking the properties and changing to the *Projected Coordinate Systems / Continental / Africa / Africa Albers Equal Area Conic.prj*.

All data were finally projected to this coordinate system and were conformed and correct.

5) Operation required for displaying the data correctly

To display data correctly we needed correctly representation of coordinate system. Then we zoomed data to the current layer in the ArcMap. To have a look at the several data at once we used transparency properties by setting *Properties / Display / Transparency* of the layers directly in ArcMap.

Model 2. Flow Chart Describing How to Solve the Second Issue

1. CONTAIN OF GIS PROJECT (DATA USED)

2. OPERATIONS

General View:

Detailed View of separate processes:

1.1. Converting vector file to raster

1.2. Clipping the raster to the necessary extent:

1.3. Clipping the raster to the necessary extent:

1.4. Calculating cropland area per capita, 2000

1.5. Estimation cropland area per capita, 2030

Outcome results can be text information in tables presented in ppt format and thematic map showing cropland area and population, possible for 2030.